

Minutes EB24-04
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
2 December 2024 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair, Reconciliation Commission
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair
Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio

1. Welcome

BW welcomed the members of the Executive Board.

2. Additions to the Agenda

Interactions with ISME Communications - PH

3. Matters Arising/Action points from the previous meeting

New and ongoing action items from previous meeting

- FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.*
Completed
- FV to circulate the outcome of the ballot on changes to the SeqCode and have it posted on the ISME and Registry websites.*
Completed
- FV to contact the various ISME ambassadors to offer our assistance in supporting or presenting a SeqCode session at any of the regional conferences.*
Ongoing. FV to interact with Kelly Wrighton, the new Director of the ISME Ambassador Program.
- LMR to finalize the 2024 report on ISME funding and forward it to BW and FV to be submitted to the ISME office.*
LMR submitted a report to claim part of the expenses.
- The EB to prepare a request for ISME funding in 2025 and submit it early in the new year.*
LMR expressed concern related to the ISME requirement that funding could not be used for the payment of persons assisting with the development of the Registry. PH will request the ISME Board to reconsider this requirement.
- IS to prepare SeqCode Version 1.1.0 and organise its posting on the Registry and ISME websites.*
Ongoing. IS will add a note indicating that this version is an update and reflects all changes in the SeqCode to date. LMR will provide IS with Version 1.03, which corrected some small errors, so IS can ensure that these were incorporated into Version 1.1.0. IS will share the final version with MC, FV and LMR to post on the various platforms.
- KK to ask the Standards Working Group to discuss possible minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.*

KK asked for clarification on what the intention of this recommendation should be, as well as where the metadata should be stored. It was agreed that the metadata should be directly linked to the genome data and should not be captured as part of the Registry.

8. FV to investigate the creation of a profile for the SeqCode on LinkedIn.

FV has created a SeqCode group linked to his profile. LMR will supply images of the SeqCode logo to be used as a banner for the group's contact page.

9. FV to investigate the creation of a Wikipedia page for the SeqCode.

Wikipedia discourages the creation of an article by a person with a connection to the topic. It was decided that the EB will proceed with the creation of a page, but that our relationship with the SeqCode will be disclosed. FV to draft a text and circulated it amongst the EB.

10. BW to contact Marike Palmer to ask her to lead a discussion to develop guidelines for the consultation process with First Peoples when taxon names linked to their culture or language are proposed.

Completed. Marike Palmer agreed to lead this discussion.

11. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.

Ongoing.

12. EB members to participate in the discussion on paratypes on RocketChat.

BW to prepare a draft proposal for possible amendments to the code for further discussion by the EB.

4. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

Legislative Commission

Version 1.1.0 of the SeqCode will be posted on the Registry and ISME websites, as per the Statutes.

Standards Working Group

The working group will still discuss the possibility of providing minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.

Registry and Nomenclature Working Group

At present 646 names have been validated and another 247 have been endorsed.

Reconciliation Commission

The commission will soon have a meeting to discuss any possible issues.

5. Discussion of Arahal et al. proposed amendments to the ICNP

FV reported that it was reported at the ICSP meeting in Florence that the proposed rules will be accepted; the formal announcement is expected shortly after 4/12/24. We are now waiting to see how these new rules will be implemented. There is uncertainty whether names in the SeqCode linked to genomes obtained from isolates will be pro-validated. The registry will alert users that SeqCode names could possibly be pre-validated in cases where the etymology and protologue were published as part of the main text of the paper and not in the Supplementary Material.

6. Dialog between the ICSP, BISMis and the SeqCode

The Bergey's Manual Trust invited the SeqCode EB to participate in constructive discussions on how potential issues that could arise from the use of both the SeqCode and the ICNP could be resolved. After

some debate it was decided that the SeqCode EB will participate in such a discussion should the other parties also agree to this dialogue. FV to inform the Bergey's Manual Trust of our decision.

7. SeqCode presence on social media

MC will create a profile for the SeqCode on Bluesky and will investigate the use of a starter pack.

8. Conference and Meeting Updates

EB members are encouraged to submit any relevant documents on the shared drive.

[\[https://fileshare.uibk.ac.at/d/83044528c7dc477597bf/?p=%2FPresentations%2F2024\]](https://fileshare.uibk.ac.at/d/83044528c7dc477597bf/?p=%2FPresentations%2F2024) Redacted

9. Interactions with ISME Communications

PH will contact Hauke Smidt to initiate discussions between Hauke and FV to establish a special category for species descriptions in ISME communications. The recent paper by Dutkiewicz et al (2024) in the journal serves as an excellent example of the type of paper that could be included in such a section.

10. AOB

IS reminded the EB that the statutes require the Chairs of the Commissions and Working Groups to provide mid-term reports in early 2025.

New action items

1. FV to circulate the minutes of this meeting to the EB for their comments and approval and to alert the SeqCode Community once it is approved.
2. FV to interact with Kelly Wrighton to offer our assistance in supporting or presenting a SeqCode session at any of the regional conferences.
3. PH to request the ISME Board to reconsider the requirement that ISME funding cannot be used for the payment of persons assisting with the development of the Registry.
4. IS to add a note indicating that this version is an update and reflects all changes in the SeqCode to date.
5. LMR to provide IS with Version 1.03, which corrected some small errors, so IS can ensure that these were incorporated into Version 1.1.0.
6. IS to share the revised version of the Code with MC, FV and LMR for posting on the various platforms.
7. LMR to supply images of the SeqCode logo to be used as a banner for the group's LinkedIn contact page.
8. FV to draft a text for a Wikipedia article on the SeqCode and circulated it amongst the EB.
9. BW to prepare a draft proposal for possible amendments to the code to include paratypes for further discussion by the EB.
10. FV to inform the Bergey's Manual Trust of our decision to participate in the proposed dialogue.
11. MC to create a profile for the SeqCode on Bluesky and to investigate the use of a starter pack.
12. PH to contact Hauke Smidt to initiate discussions between Hauke and FV to establish a special category for species descriptions in ISME communications.

13. KK, IS, MC and LMR to prepare interim reports from the commissions or working groups to be tabled at the next EB meeting.

Ongoing action items

1. KK to investigate possible RCN and ICB funding.
2. KK to ask the Standards Working Group to discuss possible minimum recommendations for metadata linked to entries.

Minutes prepared by FV: 3 December 2024

Approved: 9 December 2024